

The Study on Influence of High Frequency Noise on Sound Quality for Generator

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Abstract. As cars become quieter the sound quality of components becomes more critical in the customer perception of car quality. This requires a need of new evaluation method for the specification of component sounds. Considering that high frequency noise plays an important roll for internal noise, the noise signals in the range from 7000Hz to 8000Hz are specially emphasized. Then the acoustic evaluation parameters, such as Sound Pressure Level, Sharpness and Steadiness have been evaluated. Judged from experiences and measuring results, an abnormal noise comes from Generator, through the exchange of Generator, Sound Pressure Level and sharpness were greatly improved. At the same time, subjective evaluation also indicated that there was no complaint any more in passenger compartment. Low Sound Pressure Level, sharpness can lead to perceived high product quality.

Introduction

As car manufacturers design quieter cars to reduce power train noise, road and wind noise, the sound quality of systems with electric motors becomes more and more important for improving customer perception of overall vehicle quality [1]. Electric motors are normally used in cars for applications such as generators, power windows, windshield wipers, seat adjustment, etc, [2]. Generator sound is one of the component sounds which can be heard and perceived in passenger compartment. Because of electrical-magnetism effect, the Generator noise is inevitable to be produced when the engine is starting. The increased requirements of sound quality from customers will force the car manufacturer to focus on the noise level of components, including Generator, power window.

The human beings are very sensitive for the temporal variations of sounds, when the sounds are mainly composed of high frequency, things will become worse. In the analysis of the experiment data special attention was paid to the influence of the temporal variation sound with high frequency composition. During the development process of one new vehicle, it is complained that there is an inconstant high frequency by idling in the passenger compartment, it sounds like metal click, which leads to huge unpleasant feeling. Therefore, the experimental results were analyzed to yield information about which of the characters that were perceptually most prominent.

Method

Measurement of Noise Source. The measurement of the complained vehicle was made in a semi-anechoic room at Shanghai Volkswagen Corporation, using PAK System and two Microphones placed on engine bay and driver seat. The Microphone on driver seat was adjusted in ear position for an average male driver. Due to the complained noise comes out by idling; another Microphone was chose to be set over the engine with the height of 25 centimeters. Measurements of the sound were made for both inside and outside of the car at idle, recording time is about 60 seconds. The frequency characteristics of the test sounds are presented in Fig.1. The abnormal frequencies were between 7000 and 8000Hz. The SPL in engine bay was also recorded, which showed that the abnormal noise is sure from engine itself.

Fig. 1 Campbell of abnormal sound at driver's ear

Identification of Noise Source. Since the abnormal noise emitted no doubt from engine or it's auxiliary, the next step is to identify the location of this abnormal noise source. Except the microphone over engine, other 4 Microphones were also placed at the 4 corners in the engine bay, among them No.2 was placed near the generator. The detailed positions of 5 Microphones are presented in Fig.2. The sound pressure levels at the 5 measuring points are displayed as the function of time and frequency in Fig.3.

The results show that the noise in engine bay is time varying signal, and there is a strong correlation between No.1 and No.2 when the filter from 7000 to 8000Hz was used, the SPLs at other 3 measuring points are quite lower compared to generator. To conclude, the abnormal high frequency noise comes from generator, therefore, the quality of it should be take good care of. For generator, the reason for such an abnormal noise maybe comes from the effect of electric-magnetism.

In order to verify the noise source is not the other components but Generator, a generator with another brand was also tested. SPLs with band pass filter from 7000 to 8000Hz are presented in Fig.4. The measuring point is placed over engine with the height of 25 centimeters. The results showed significant differences between the two Generators, the original generator is time-varying with amplitude varies from about 65dB to 70dB; and the amplitude of another one is nearly constant with time varying .furthermore, the amplitude is only about 63.5dB. Subjective evaluation also verified the same improvement; People can sit in the passenger compartment without annoyance.

Fig. 2 5 measuring points in engine bay

Fig. 3 Campbell at 5 measuring points

Fig. 4 SPL with BP filter (7k~8k) as a function of time

Results and Discussion

Objective Evaluation. Car manufacturers have expressed the need for simple models which facilitate communication with suppliers. Standard procedures for measurements of noise are still based on A-weighted sound pressure level in Octave or 1/3-octave band. The traditional approach has its own shortcomings, which are ambiguous and unclear for non-acoustic people, because it is difficult to judge sound quality only by sound pressure level. Sound quality is a sophisticated concept, not only includes sound pressure level, but also psychoacoustic parameters, such as loudness, sharpness, steadiness, roughness and fluctuation, and so on.

Modeling Perceived Product Quality as Functions of Acoustic Quantities

The approach has been to first use the psychoacoustic parameters for detailed information about the underlying phenomena leading to the perception of annoyance and overall product quality.

Sharpness. Sharpness has been used to partially quantify sound quality in examples such as measuring engine noise, and some domestic appliances such as vacuum cleaners and hair dryers. It has also been used in the calculation of a sensory pleasantness metric and an unbiased annoyance metric [3]. The most important parameters influencing sharpness are the spectral content and the centre frequency of narrow-band sounds.

Sharpness is a measure of the high frequency content of a sound, the greater the proportion of high frequencies the 'sharper' the sound. Where the high frequency content of a sound is important to a product's quality, then sharpness can be a useful measure. Sharpness is a hearing sensation related to frequency and independent of loudness. Sharpness corresponds to the sensation of a sharp, painful, high-frequency sound and is the comparison of the amount of high frequency energy to the total energy. The sharpness algorithm computes sharpness from the sound pressure signal

waveform, the 1/3-octave band spectrum calculated over the frequency range 25 Hz to 12.5 kHz, or the specific loudness.

However, sharpness is a metric which has not yet been standardized. Consequently there are several methods to calculate the metric including: Von Bismarck's method [4] which introduces the idea of a weighted first moment calculation, Aures's method [5], which is a modified version of Von Bismarck's equation and Zwicker & Fastl's method [3] which is a version of Von Bismarck's equation with a modified weighting curve. Fig.5. shows the sharpness of two different generators. The optimized generator has rather lower sharpness than original generator, which helps to explain why original generator sounds so metallic.

Fig. 5 Sharpness according to Aures as a function of time

Steadiness. A metric for steadiness was suggested and tested - Relative SPL Deviation (RSD) defined as

$$RSD = \frac{(SPL_{\max} - SPL_{\min})}{((SPL_{\max} + SPL_{\min}) / 2)} \quad (1)$$

RSD reflects the variation or unevenness degree of noise signals, the result for original generator is 0.078693, and the result for another optimized generator is only 0.00788, which showed same result with subjective judgments.

Summary

A-weighted sound pressure level showed a slightly lower correlation with subjective judgments for generator noise, but sharpness and steadiness showed agreement with subjective evaluations. The most important parameters influencing sharpness are the spectral content and the centre frequency of narrow-band sounds. A good generator was considered to be of high quality if it was quiet, less sharp and steady. This was explained by the increasing trend of loudness, sharpness and amplitude variation of generator, leading to a bad perception of sound quality.

From the results of this study the following recommendations can be made: focus should be on the content of high frequency of generator noise if it sounds metallic.

The generator should have low SPL, low sharpness and minimal variations of high frequency noise.

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